

IPERION HS

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D.1.2 Quality Outcomes

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Abstract

(300-500 words)

This deliverable provides the detailed outputs of quality monitoring, reckoned periodically for the entire duration of the Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure on Heritage Science project (M1-48). One of the primary goals as outlined in IPERION HS D1.1 has been to establish and put into action an elementary quality and evaluation system based on the assessment and flexibility for all the services provided through IPERION HS and its various outputs. Specifically, an ad-hoc set of 16 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been implemented and monitored including those qualitative and quantitative recommended by ESFRI and others suited for purpose through the long experience of the IPERION HS consortium currently projected towards the European Research infrastructure for Cultural Heritage (E-RIHS) now in its implementation project phase (E-RIHS IP). It will be highlighted that main outcomes regard the project's principal activities namely, transnational access; joint research; dissemination and training; communication and administration. The established KPIs have been designed to provide an accurate representation of the project's development and trends concerning adherence to predetermined goals and targets, as well as the contentment of access service users and recipients of training and dissemination initiatives of HS Academy. It will be shown how periodic outcomes on performance, output and impacts have also permitted potential problems to be identified and have supported the appropriate actions to be taken. The lessons learnt for quality in IPERION HS will be used to direct the progression and necessary commitment of E-RIHS into the functioning European RI ecosystem considering that the KPIs shall be fed into a monitoring at the end of their ten years on the ESFRI roadmap to assess a potential Landmark status. Finally, the updated fundamental set of ethical principles and considerations by which all those working within the project and, later, under the E-RIHS brand are bound to are herein provided.

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Abbreviations

Abbreviations	Expansion
IPERION HS	Integrating Platforms for the European Research Infrastructure ON Heritage Science (this Project)
E-RIHS	E-RIHS European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science
E-RIHS IP	European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science- Implementation Phase (Horizon CSA project, GA nr. 101079148)
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
RI	Research Infrastructure
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KPI _E	An ESFRI recommended KPI based on a common approach across Research Infrastructures to monitor their performance based on narrated Key Performance Indicators.
nr.	number
WP	Work Package

IPERION HS QUALITY MONITORING

1. Introduction

The IPERION HS project has provided an integrated activity towards the establishment of the distributed pan-European research infrastructure for heritage science (E-RIHS). Currently in its implementation project phase, E-RIHS has applied for the legal form of an ERIC and aims to progress to the operational phase of the RI where on-going developments of the quality manual and procedures for ascertaining the quality of services and activities under the E-RIHS brand are being made. Concominantly, IPERION HS has supported this long-term development through collecting and providing thorough data for the tailored quality and evaluation system of services rendered through the project and for its other outcomes based on flexibility and self-evaluation.

Specifically, monitoring in IPERION HS has aimed to enable a regular exchange and transparency within the consortium through assessing the quality of project activities namely transnational access, training and dissemination, communication and administration through a dedicated set of KPIs as shown in table 1. The implementation of KPIs, at this project level, have been mindful of the recommendations of ESFRI in the WORKING GROUP REPORT Monitoring of Research Infrastructures Performance December of 2019 [1]. This work furthermore builds on the recommendations of the 2016 ESFRI Projects monitoring exercise to *better describe E-RIHS indicators* delivered in 2021 [2]. The core text of this deliverable is dedicated to outlining the set of KPIs that aligned with the specific objectives of IPERION HS to fulfil RACER criteria: Relevant, Accepted, Credible, Easy to monitor and Robust. Each KPI has been accompanied by its narrative with definition, method of calculation, and other information concerning its applicability.

Table 1: Table of key performance indicators periodically monitored in IPERION HS

ACTIVITIES CATEGORY	DERIVED FROM	IDENTIFICATION NUMBER	KEY PERFORMANCE INDICATOR
ACCESS	ESFRI	KPI _{E1}	Yearly number of users requests;
		KPI _{E2}	Yearly number of granted proposals
		KPI _{E3}	Share of users per EU country
		KPI _{E4}	Share of users from outside the EU, including research teams with one or more non-EU nationals
		KPI _{Apublication}	no. of publications in at least pre-print form acknowledging IPERION HS / no. of accesses
	E-RIHS	KPI _{UserSupport}	score from all contacts for ease of resolution of queries / perfect score
		KPI _{demand}	number of requests / available slots
KPI _{feedback}		score from all users / perfect score	
RESEARCH	ESFRI	KPI _{Rpublication}	no. of publications in at least pre-print form related to joint research activities (start at M24)
DISSEMINATION + TRAINING		KPI _{E5}	Yearly total no. participants in dissemination events organized by IPHS partners
		KPI _{E6}	Yearly no. attendees in education events (Training camps and summer schools)
		KPI _{E7}	Yearly no. of webinar hours offered in IPHS
COMMUNICATION		KPI _{E8}	Yearly no. of website accesses
		KPI _{E9}	Average duration of single website access
		KPI _{E10}	Social media insight (yearly no. of people engaged)
ADMINISTRATION		KPI _{Efficiency}	Average delay in weeks of the submission of IPHS deliverables No. of weeks delay / no. of deliverables submitted

In order to gather these quality outputs, IPERION HS, has specifically created and used the digital dashboard where it has been possible to extract data in real-time to be able to reliably report and be useful in the calculation of some of the proposed indicators. This has assisted IPERION HS to establish best practice in developing and implementing KPIs, and to ensure that statistics could be presented to stakeholders during periodic evaluations and that they could be made available for future consultation. The quality outputs of each KPI for the entire duration of the IPERION HS project are then graphically represented and discussed at length.

The quality outcomes in this deliverable have been determined in effort WP2-4 physical platform data and the single-entry point Userhelpdesk with regards to the nine KPIs for access; WP7 and subtask T8.2 have provided all information for the three KPIs regarding dissemination and training; subtask T8.3 has been responsible for the collection and reporting of the three KPIs for communication. Finally, WP8 central activities and coordination office account for the presented administration monitoring.

2. Outcomes of IPERION HS KPIs

As aforementioned, each single KPI is subsequently presented in order and accordance with activity category- access, dissemination and training, communication and administration:

2.1 ACCESS

As given in figure 1, the rationale behind the **KPIE1. yearly nr. of users requests** is tabulated. It has been possible to map the number of users who have requested access to the physical platform services of IPERION HS. The number of users is all those who are part of the user group as determined in the submitted application form to the platform. *Where applications are multi-facility, the number of user requests is corrected by the number of different facilities requested where possible.* The internal dashboard does not consider this aspect which becomes predominantly manual and open to error. In any case, from the relative bar chart, the number of users requesting each platform are given where it has been possible to calculate the yearly number of users requesting services during IPERION HS. Specifically, the numbers can be noted where 3 calls for access in 2021 saw requests from 845 users, 2022 with 2 calls a total of 631 users and finally in 2023 for the final last two calls 441 users. The reduction of number of users yearly can be explained due to the fact that the first year had three calls and in the final year there was not a 7th call for access for the MOLAB platform. **The average yearly number of 639 users requested access to the IPHS TNA programme.**

Figure 1: KPIE1. Yearly nr. of users requests- tabulated description and charted outcomes

To verify that the demand for each service offered and that promotion of access is sufficient to attract a high inflow of interested researchers, the **KPI_{DEMAND}** was introduced by the experience of the consortium. The demand was calculated for each service in each platform after every call deadline using the actual numbers of access requested for every service/available access slots per service as given in the grant agreement. It was possible to notice which services were highly requested and which indeed were under requested at any given call. In figure 2 the trends of demand can be appreciated at each call where for the duration of IPERION HS **the average demand for all TNA services is 1.5, satisfying the project target for demand which was set at >1,2**. Breaking down the averages for each platform shows that overall ARCHLAB had a demand of 0,74; FIXLAB 1,05 and MOLAB 2,92. This KPI is highly informative when adjustments to offers and number of slots can be made- as will be yearly for E-RIHS.

Figure 2: KPI_{DEMAND}-tabulated description and charted outcomes for each platform

As can be observed in figure 3, the outcomes of **KPIE2. yearly nr. of granted proposals** are provided. Through the monitoring of the numbers of proposals that have been submitted, actually 316 in total, to those which are actually selected for access (210 proposals) have provided information regarding the peer-reviewed high scientific excellence of research proposals. ARCHLAB selected a total of 29 research projects; FIXLAB granted a total of 160 projects and MOLAB 21 projects. *This number considers only the granted number of projects, not whether they were all actually finalized and carried.* The final outcomes of each platform are discussed in the relevant deliverables D2.2, D3.2 and D4.2 respectively with regards to units of promised TNA and actual TNA carried out. Expressed yearly with less projects selected during 2022 likely following the queuing of projects during the pandemic and subsequent saturation of facilities, **an average number of 70 single and multi-facility projects were successfully reviewed and listed for TNA yearly.** This indicator provides a measure of the efficiency of operations.

Figure 3: KPI_{E2}. Yearly nr. of granted proposals,-tabulated description and charted outcomes

KPI_{E3} Share of users per EU Country was monitored for the entire project’s duration. *This data takes into consideration all the successful user group members and not only the user group leader.* The indicator provides a measure of the extent to which IPHS has played a role to facilitate and optimise the use of TNA facilities whilst continuing to develop a European user community. The increase of the number of new users (experiments/projects) cannot be visualized through this KPI. The vast dispersion across Europe of TNA users can be observed in figure 4, specifically in the order of percentage the countries whose researchers availed of the access to physical platform services- Italy (~20%), France (16%), Belgium (~10%) and Spain (~7%)

Figure 4: KPI_{E3}. Share of users per EU Country-entire duration of IPERION HS

Figure 5 displays the obtained results as percentage of the **KPI_{E4}. Share of users per Country outside the EU**. This indicator highlights the international relevance and attractiveness of the services provided in IPHS. A rather small proportion of access was granted beyond Europe exclusively

according to the assessed scientific excellence of project proposals. Countries such as USA and south Africa made up 0,85% and 0,66% of users respectively.

KPI_{E3} Share of users per EU Country and **KPI_{E4}. Share of users per Country outside the EU** can be utilized to also provide total numbers of users served which is here considered as 1038 people in Europe and 26 international users. The total number of users served in IPERION HS rests at 1064- (a small margin of error should be considered if not all multi-facility users within a single project were correctly counted as this had to be done manually). In any case, this number comfortably surpasses the targeted number of users for TNA as indicated in the GA of 759 users.

Figure 5: KPI_{E4}. Share of users per Country outside the EU-entire duration of IPERION HS

A basic evaluation system for the services rendered through IPERION HS was set based on **feedback from users**. A simple feedback form was established and implemented to gather feedback from users of the access services as part of the post-access duties. The collection of feedback ensures that the opinion of users is taken into consideration so that the operational E-RIHS can become more equipped to meet their specific and immediate needs rather than basing strategies on assumptions. At the time of writing, results have been collected regarding access user satisfaction of 120 projects, slightly more than 57% of access projects carried out. The survey was carried out online with statistics immediately provided, making this a low manual monitoring tool, however the low uptake of users to provide the survey is likely due to the automated request and lack of follow-up. The survey was composed of a series of questions to monitor each step of access provision, answered on inserting a rating from 1 (very poor) to 10 (excellent). Among the questions, those highlighted in figure 6 were monitored- namely support from the UserHelpdesk **KPI_{USERSUPPORT}** (average score 0,89) and **KPI_{FEEDBACK}** relative to the overall rating of the access (average score 0,93). A free text field also permitted suggestions to be formulated regarding any aspect of the TNA services and gathered positive comments and highlighted challenges which were shared internally within the platforms. Such comments served to drive development in all aspects related to access service provision.

Figure 6: KPI_{USERSUPPORT} and KPI_{FEEDBACK} extrapolated from the access user satisfaction survey

The number of **publications based on research**, derived from combined access to TNA platforms (WP2; WP3; WP4) and from the joint research activities (WP5) performed using the facilities/resources of IPERION HS consortium provides a measure of the extent of those services and research facilities, the size of the user community and the combined performance of the two in transforming the experimental results or data into publishable material.

Much of the published output have been captured using commercial databases such as Clarivate and WOS which contain mainly articles published in peer-reviewed journals. Full information regarding proceedings papers, book chapters, books and technical reports etc are currently being provided by project partners to locate all publications. However, it has not been possible to distinguish the precise number of publications derived specifically from access activities as much data collected is still in the elaboration phase and it could be necessary to gather the information directly from the users. It is to be expected in any case that a flourish of publications will follow in the next years. At the time of writing KPI_{publication} showcases 36 publications mentioning the funding received from IPERION HS as observed in figure 7 and relate to the topics in order- chemistry, spectroscopy, material sciences, archaeology, geosciences and so forth. It can be mentioned that this project aimed to include the new community of archaeology and new instrumentations for geosciences- the resulting publications show such success of their inclusion.

Figure 7: KPI_{Publication} joint research and access activities

2.2 DISSEMINATION and TRAINING

Extensive **Dissemination and Training activities of the HS Academy** have included a series of 12 webinars, 16 lectures, 2 training camps, 2 doctoral summer schools and 5 user meetings. Capturing the data related to the **KPI_{E5} yearly no. attendees in dissemination events** (webinars, lectures, user meetings) and **KPI_{E7} yearly no. hours for webinars and lectures** provide an indicator of the reach and engagement with which IPERION HS has been able to attract participants to attend. Data related to **KPI_{E6} yearly no. attendees in education events** (training camps and summer schools) highlights how much accessible training the HS Academy has been able to offer the Heritage Science community. The data also provides an indication of the successful communication strategy for the outreach for each and any event/lecture etc. Following each of these events a **feedback survey** was sent to all participants where the overall satisfaction out of 10 was given at 8,6 for webinars; 8,8 for user meetings and lectures; 9,4 for the training camps and finally 9,3 for the doctoral summer schools. Quantitative data are collectively given in figure 8.

Figure 8: KPI₅; KPI₆; KPI₇ related to activities in the categories of dissemination and training.

2.3 COMMUNICATION

Within the ESFRI category of outreach to the public, **KPI₈ yearly number of website accesses; KPI₉ average duration of single website access and KPI₁₀ social media insight** have been monitored periodically for the duration of the IPERION HS project by the Coordination office’s Communication officer. Although only these numbers were mapped, the actual work of the media/public relations in IPHS is visible in each of the activities carried out- from all the advertising, publicity, promotional materials etc where the impact of press and communication actions have actually raised awareness of the IPHS and E-RIHS mission, providing understanding of research in the fields of operations and societal relevance of results. In this sense, the communication strategy evaluation process is predictive that may be used to support and improve future communication efforts where the KPIs can identify the audience's behavior and inform on the implementation of more efficient strategies to communicate in a reliable, transparent, open, and consistent manner.

Specifically, indicators are captured of how useful and engaging the website is as well as indicating the presence and engagement via the web and social media presence. The analytical tools (Google Analytics, Twitter analytics) enabled frequent tracking with rapid and low maintenance methods. Trends in the growth of website accesses and duration of access could be mapped from 2022 through to 2024. Numbers regarding social media presence also increased where all numbers are provided in figure 9.

Figure 9: KPI₈; KPI₉; KPI₁₀ related to activities in the ESFRI category of Outreach to the Public.

2.4 ADMINISTRATION

Administration has to do with the background operations of the IPERION HS Project and, in the future, E-RIHS ERIC. Within IPERION HS the administrative KPI, **KPI_EEFFICIENCY**, is related to the optimizing management objective of ESFRI. This specific KPI regards the count of timely submission of deliverables for the IPERION HS project. At the moment of writing, 28 deliverables have been submitted spanning the project, 13 of which were submitted and justified for late arrival, 4 of which following a lengthy delay. In any case, the average delay in weeks of the submission of IPHS deliverables calculated as nr. of weeks delay / nr. of deliverables submitted is almost 3, falling short of the target of 1 week.

In the perspective of the future ERIC, this KPI will not be relevant and will be replaced by a KPI measuring the efficiency of the top management in readying the reports and plans needed for the convocation of the Ordinary General Assembly during the first weeks of each year, so that the final activity plan and recommendations stemming from the Assembly may start being implemented as early as possible. When E-RIHS ERIC starts working, all those KPI that refer to the outreach to potential users of the technical assets and beneficiaries/clients of knowledge dissemination, as well as those KPI reckoned from feedback on the whole process will be of crucial importance in administrative terms. Such KPIs are KPI_{usersupport}, KPI_{demand} and KPI_{feedback} (see Table 1). One or more KPIs directly related to clerical work may be judged necessary and developed under E-RIHS ERIC.

3. ETHICS

Independently of their field, scientific researchers are expected to maintain the highest standards of professional integrity, and compliance with all relevant codes of conduct and ethics. IPERION-HS (in the future E-RIHS) is Humanist in nature and aimed to study and preserve Culture within the scope of Heritage Science. Ethics within the IPERION-HS partnership is understood as a set of principles by which all those working within its scope are bound to abide. Those principles are consequent through procedures followed in all operations.

Principles

i. Respect for persons

Researchers and other professionals should maintain the highest moral standards irrespective of the difficulties and limitations that at any moment might be raised. They should have concern for others and in general treat them as they would normally want to be treated in likewise conditions. Whatever their own personal opinions, professionals should behave without prejudice against others, treating them likewise irrespective of gender, nationality, ethnicity, religion, age, sexual orientation, gender expression, presence of disabilities, educational background, professional origin or other personal attributes or aspects through which diversity manifests itself.

People with reduced autonomy should be cared for, so as to ensure that the eventual influence of their condition in their participation to the work is minimized.

Tutelage of students or apprentices is to be regarded as a trust. Wherever possible, recognised intermediaries should be used so that those under formation have always two different contact points, e. g. one tutor and one supervisor. This should be strictly adhered to whenever young people under the age of consent are involved.

Students and apprentices should be given as much autonomy of decision in research as possible and treated with the same consideration due to colleagues, respectfully and without exploitation, having only in view the promotion of their learning and professional development in safety and without undue constraints.

Researchers should treat colleagues throughout the partnership respectfully and as equals, and through cooperative actions diffuse knowledge by both teaching and learning. They should share ideas openly whenever confidentiality of procedures or results is not at stake, and give credit for the contributions of others. Before any team work is started, the researchers involved must agree on and comply with practices for data ownership and sharing, authorship, publication, peer review (if applicable) and cooperation in general.

ii. Respect for heritage values

The importance of tangible cultural heritage depends on a belief system that attributes significance and relative weight to an asset, be it a cathedral or a ring. A scientist will not put in cause in any manner an established system of values unless grounded on largely unquestionable research results. Whenever research results contradict, in a relevant manner, values upon which the importance of a heritage asset rests (e. g. by strongly suggesting a different, eventually more recent, chronology) those results must at least be reassessed and eventually the whole instrumental process repeated, possibly after a new sampling and by a different team using an alternate technology, before the results are published or made public in any manner. The owner or entity responsible for the asset will be informed in detail of the conclusions and their ground before any dissemination is made.

Any sampling of a tangible heritage asset will decrease its value, even if negligibly. Therefore, it must be carefully considered on a basis of potential gain versus potential harm. Sample sizes must be

adequate given the asset sampled and the purpose: as small as possible but not so small that they may end up being unfit.

When sampling a physical asset researchers will first seek consent from the owner or the entity responsible for its conservation. On seeking authorization, they will inform on the objective, number and size of samples needed, and method of sampling. They will also establish an agreement on the ultimate destination of the test items and any remainders.

In all cases, the owner or the entity responsible for the conservation will be offered the possibility to witness the sampling procedure and thenceforward be considered primary stakeholders of the research, be informed of the results before any dissemination and, if not co-authors, their participation will be acknowledged in publications using the results.

Samples of heritage assets, test items obtained thereof and remainders are themselves heritage assets with associated values and must be treated as such, in particular caring that all information related to the sampling is obtained and kept traceable to each sample.

If applicable, scientists should aim at the preservation of test items and remainders associated with the information pertaining to the sampling and instrumental procedures applied, towards their future availability for further research without the need to re-sample.

iii. Beneficence (Do Good)

The definition of beneficence is linked with outcomes that are beneficial to others and to the society at large. This principle states that research should aim at some positive outcome that will advance knowledge and our understanding of phenomena under the rule of science, towards a positive purpose such as the enhancement of some of the values of cultural heritage.

Results should be shared with the research community and the public at large through diffusion media and integration in accessible databases.

Beneficence is also connected with doing no harm: professionals should comply with safety policies and procedures and improve them when possible to safeguard from undue risk students, apprentices, all other team members and themselves. They should respect and protect life and the environment avoiding any aggression and following the highest health and safety standards, including the disposal of waste and waste products having in view, not only immediate consequences, but also possible risks in the long run.

Scientists must be aware of their role in the sequence going from academic research, pre-practice research and practical implementation. Conclusions made under one context may be misleading and ultimately detrimental, sometimes grievously, when applied in a specific situation. Therefore, researchers should not suggest or propose practical application with insufficient data validation and lack of practical demonstration.

iv. Fairness

All activities and their outcomes are to be developed or handled in a fair way, transparent to all participants. Peer reviews of applications, performance or proposed publications should be conducted in a righteous manner. Whenever possible, there must be clear rules known to those being assessed and all notes should be clearly explained and justified. There should be an established system of appeal involving a third party. Registers of all consequential remarks and decisions should be maintained and made available to those deciding on any claims or appeals.

Authorship of papers and similar diffusion media should be based simultaneously on: i) substantial contributions to the conception of the research; or the acquisition and interpretation of data for the work; and ii) drafting the texts or revising them critically; and iii) approval of the version to be published in a way that makes the person fully accountable for the contents. Unless there is a clear preliminary understanding otherwise, only those meeting the three criteria should be deemed as

authors or co-authors; all those not meeting the criteria but having nevertheless significant contributions should be acknowledged. The order of author names has a meaning that varies with the field but should follow clear rules known previously to all in writing, and agreed between all team members. IPERION-HS recommends to all researchers within its partnership to be generous with students and apprentices giving them, whenever fair, a position as authors that will enhance the development of their careers.

By default, and as known to all and agreed between the team, a measure of confidentiality on processes and outcomes must be established before publication. Subsequent results must necessarily refer the original publication or acknowledge the sources of the research lines being pursued.

v. Quality

Quality in all of its forms should always be one of the pillars of scientific research. Within Ethics, IPERION-HS researchers and other professionals should strive to remain informed and apply the most recent advances in their field. They should share ideas and information, use instruments of known accuracy, keep complete laboratory registers, maintain professional moderation in their conduct and publications, and give due credit to the contributions of others.

Conflicts of interest and scientific misconduct, such as bold or biased conclusions based on insufficient data, fabrication or plagiarism, are incompatible with ethical principles. Experimental procedures should be fully reproducible and the disclosure of results in scientific media should always include all information needed to replicate the experiments or measurements to a reasonably uncertainty level. Public comments on scientific matters should be made with care and accuracy. Questionable conclusions should be presented as hypotheses and premature or exaggerated statements should be absolutely avoided.

“Research is a quest for new knowledge, with critical and systematic verification and peer review. Honesty, openness, a systematic approach and documentation are fundamental preconditions for achieving this goal.” [3]

Other sources consulted: [4; 5; 6; 7].

4. Conclusions

The Quality outcomes of IPERION HS regarding main project activities namely, transnational access; joint research; dissemination and training; communication and administration have been discussed through the outputs of a set of KPIs. The selected ESFRI and E-RIHS PP KPIs have been aimed at forming a reliable picture of the evolution of the Project in terms of conformity with set goals, progression of important factors and satisfaction of users. All sixteen IPHS KPIs have been periodically monitored, nine KPIs for access; three KPIs regarding dissemination and training; three KPIs for communication and a single KPI for administration. The established KPIs have provided a valid image of the project's development and trends concerning an overall adherence to predetermined goals and targets, as well as satisfaction of access service users and recipients of training and dissemination initiatives. The acquired knowledge for quality monitoring in IPERION HS will be fully exploited to guide the progression, development and commitment of the E-RIHS quality monitoring system into the operational European RI ecosystem.

The most recent version of the core set of ethic guidelines and standards that all project participants and anyone who associate with the E-RIHS brand is also provided based on main principles of respect, beneficence, fairness and quality.

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